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A Speech Act Analysis Of The Inaugural Speeches Of President Bola Ahmed Tinubu And President Muhammadu Buhari

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ABSTRACT

The research focuses on finding out the speech acts used by President Bola Ahmed Tinubu and the former President Muhammadu Buhari in their Inaugural Speeches. Searle (1969) Speech act Theory used as theoretical framework serving as a focal lens through which the study was visualised while mixed method used for data analysis. Therefore, the purposive sampling technique is used in selecting 40 sentences from each inaugural speech for analysis based on Searle (1969) categorisation of speech act, which provide the avenue and means of answering the research questions. The downloaded version of both inaugural speeches constitute the main data. Findings of the study indicate that, assertive speech act is the most dominant speech act used in both speeches. The result of the study shows that, Assertive Speech acts serve as the basic tools President Bola Ahmed Tinubu and President Muhammadu Buhari use to convey their believes and to obtain support from their audiences, and illocutionary acts are used to depict the past, present and future situations in the country and to inspire public confidence in the governments.

Keywords: Speech acts, inaugural speech

INTRODUCTION

The presidential speech is a link or relationship between the president and the people. In the Nigeria, traditionally inaugural speech is delivered on May 29th every year, which has been the hand-over day from one democratically elected administration to the other since 1999. Pragmatic base approach is a tool of decoding meaning from any speech in a more appropriate way. Therefore, understanding the context becomes important in order to convey exactly what the speaker intention through his utterances (Della, 2018). It is against this background that Speech Act Theory is used to assume meaning and intentions in the inaugural speeches of President Bola Ahmed Tinubu and President Muhammadu Buhari to Nigerians. Conversely, the use of language in political speech making and the way it is used to make the speech meaningful to the hearer is a very important aspect that must be looked into, and this reason has

prompted the researcher into undertaking a speech act analysis of President Bola Ahmed Tinubu and former president Muhammadu Buhari's inaugural speech. Linguists often subjected different kinds of speeches to different analysis. In Nigeria, different studies have been conducted on pragmatic acts of political speeches while others focused on the stylistic features. For instance, Josia and Johnson (2012) examine the pragmatic features of the Inaugural speech of President Barrack Obama of America and President Goodluck Jonathan.

Olaniyi (2010) focused on the pragmatic features of the 2007 inaugural address of President Umaru Musa Yara'dua, Ayeomoi and Akinkulore (2012) carried out a pragmatic analysis of victory in the inaugural speech of President Umaru Musa Yaradua as opposed to Olaniyi. The analysis of most of these studies are based on pragmatic act theory proposed by Mey (2001) and Austin (1962) speech act theory.

The present study is motivated by the desire to decode the meaning of some utterances in the inaugural speeches of President Bola Ahmed Tinubu and President Muhammadu Buhari, using the pragmatic base approach. The research work attempts to unpack this utterance to reveal how the speakers use language to convey their intentions. In essence, this study attempts to delineate how political language is contextualized in the Nigerian situation. By so doing, the study examines the structure, communicative effectiveness and expressive purposes of such political utterance. Different studies have also been on pragmatic acts of political speeches, which includes; Hazhar & Shamaila (2021) which studies on the Speech Act Analysis of Joseph R. Biden, Jr's Inaugural Address on 20th January 2021, as the 46th President of the USA. Salwa (2022) studied the Analysis of Jokowi's Commissive Speech Acts in 2014 and 2019 Inaugural Address. Akinwotun (2018) examines patterns of language use in the inaugural speeches of Governor Olusegun Mimiko of Ondo state, using a stylistic approach that blends with Michael Halliday's systemic functional Grammar. Also, Sobola (2020) examines the cognition of Metaphorical text in President Muhammadu Buhari's Inaugural Speech, using a theory of lexical concept and cognitive model propounded by Vivian Evans. and many others. However, the present study analyses the inaugural speeches of President Bola Ahmed Tinubu and President Muhammadu Buhari, while a little effort has been put into President Bola Ahmed Tinubu because it is relatively a new speech, and it has not been looked into with the former President of Nigeria, Muhammadu Buhari to find out the communicative intentions behind their speeches. This study fills the gap by examining the use of speech acts to perform actions and convey their intentions to the citizens of Nigeria using Searle's (1969) theory focusing more on his classification of illocutionary act thereby looking into the differences and similarities that occur in both speeches.

The Concept of Speech Act

The British Philosopher J.L. Austin introduced speech act theory, he is considered the proponent of the Theory in (1962) in his book *How to do Things With Word*, later modified by the American Philosopher John Searle (1969). Speech acts are divided into three major categories. Thus, locutionary, illocutionary, and perlocutionary. Several attempts were made in classifying speech acts (illocutionary acts), e.g., Austin (1962), Searle (1975), Bach and Harnish (1979), Leech (1983). The most prominent is that of Austin, who came up with a classification that became the basis for later classifications, while Searle revised and re-classified Austin's categories. The other subsequent attempts, however, are in general either modifications or refinements of either Austin's or Searle's models of classifications. Austin (1989) summarized his classification as follows to say that the verdictive is an exercise of judgment, the exercitive is an assertion of influence or exercising of power, the commissive is an assuming of an obligation or declaring of an intention, the behabitive is the adopting of an attitude, and the expositive is the clarifying of reasons, arguments, and communications.

Searle practically did not follow Austin's classification (the only thing he retained was Austin's commissives). He instead came up with his own five basic types of speech acts; namely: assertives, directives, commissives, expressives, and declarations.

Theoretical Framework

The study adopts the speech act theory of Pragmatics for the analysis of data. Speech act theory was introduced by The British Philosopher J.L. Austin he is considered the original author of the concept 'Speech Act Theory ' (1962) in his book *How to do Things With Words*. It was modified later by the American Philosopher John Searle (1969). Austin worked on the development of the first organized notion of words just like human behaviour. The goal of Austin's idea has been to tear down the language point of view which would find "truth conditions" fundamental to comprehend language. He extracted his method depending on the idea that language usage for doing functions. The main theme of Austin's *How to Do Things with Words* is the replacement of the original distinction between performatives and constatives by a general theory of speech acts. The original distinction (the "special theory") was supposed to be a distinction between utterances, which are statements or descriptions, and utterances, which are acts, such as, promises, apologies, bets, or warnings. It is supposed to be a distinction between utterances which are sayings and utterances which are doings. Searle is considered one of the most important developers of speech act theory. He modifies Austin's theory on the level of taxonomy. Searle reviews the classification of Austin because it depends on interfering standards. He notes that the distinction between verbs of Speech act theory and speech acts is not explained by Austin. He classifies Speech Acts into five categories (assertive, directives, commissives, expressive and declaratives). He also mentions four types of conditions that control the successful performance of the illocutionary act which include (The Propositional Content Conditions, Preparatory Conditions, and Sincerity Conditions). He also improved on Austins (1962) Speech Act theory by distinguishing between two types of speech acts: Direct and Indirect Speech Acts. Searle proposes that any linguistic unit that is used in interaction has the ability to create a performance, " all linguistics communication involves linguistiuc acts" Searle (1969) Therefore, the speech act theory of Searle (1969) perfectly fits this because the research deals with finding out how both Presidents use words to perform an action.

METHODOLOGY

A mixed research method was employed for this study, data were extracted and analyzed from the daily trust published during the inaugural speech. The study employs the purposive sampling, which is a non-probability sampling technique in selecting 40 sentences from each inaugural speech, the first 20 sentences and last 20 sentences. Purposive sampling as the name implies, aids the researcher in having a free hand to select relevant data related to the study, therefore, 40 sentences each were extracted from the printed version of the inaugural speech, which are purposively selected by the researcher.

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

The data presentation and analysis were carried out in correspondence with one of the objective of the study, which is to find out the assertive speech acts used in the Inaugural speech of President Bola Ahmed Tinubu and President Muhammadu Buhari. The aim is to find out how they use words to convey their intentions to the citizens of Nigeria.

ASSERTIVE SPEECH ACTS IN PRESIDENT BOLA AHMED TINUBU'S INAUGURAL SPEECH

Assertive expresses the belief of the speaker. The verbs, which clarify this category are, claim, conclude, state, assert, report, e.t.c

It has been noticed that assertive is used in both speeches, which are labelled

Excerpt A – President Bola Ahmed Tinubu's Inaugural speech

Excerpt B – President Muhammadu Buhari's Inaugural Speech

From the first speech, which is excerpt A, the following were extracted.

Excerpt A 1

I stand before you honoured to assume the sacred mandate you have given me.

Explicit: Asserts President Bola Ahmed Tinubu's acceptance of the mandate at the same time, acknowledging the peoples role in giving him the mandate to lead. This expresses the assertive act of acknowledging the democratic process they have entrusted him with..

Implicit: It expresses gratitude and honour for the people for their trust, and legitimizing his position

The above statement, comprises of making a statement of assertion. He believes that the citizens of Nigeria voted for him and that is why he is standing as the President of Nigeria. The leadership is considered as "sacred", something spiritual. This usage ties the mandate with the idea of spirituality in a country where the people are often considered religious. The usage of "sacred mandate" further legitimatizes his position and purifies the election that brought him to power and as being challenged at the time of this speech. He believes that the people voted him so that he can fulfil their dreams. This utterance is a direct speech, the President is directly referring to the people who voted for him that are the citizens who believed and voted for him to fulfil the dreams of Nigerians.

Excerpt A 2

My love for this country is abiding

Explicit: Asserts his enduring love for Nigeria, which is a motivation he has to serve the nation

Implicit: This express patriotism, a sense of loyalty and dedication to Nigeria as a nation implying that his love for the country is the motivation to lead. This is intended to project sincerity and establish credibility, demonstrating genuinely to Nigeria's well being

The sentence made by president Bola Ahmed Tinubu, is a statement that asserts the President love for the country where he explained it to be abiding, that is to say his love for the country is continuous never ending. He is also affirming that his love for the country is ever lasting, which can be true or false. He attributed his love for the country as "abiding" this usage makes it look like president Bola Ahmed Tinubu has an everlasting love for the country, this ties his love for the country as undying that is to say he will continue loving the country.

Excerpt A3

My confidence in its people, unwavering.

Explicit: This statement explicitly states confidence that he has on the people of Nigeria

Implicit: expresses faith, conveys trust in the people's ability to work together with him, it equally reassures Nigerians, and inspires confidence in the people

The assertive speech act is being used in this sentence is an assertion of how confident President Bola Ahmed Tinubu is in the people of the country which is strong. It is a statement of fact, and can be either true or false depending on him. President Bola Ahmed Tinubu is making a statement about the unwavering confidence he has on the people of Nigeria. The usage of the word "unwavering" links his confidence in the people of Nigeria as unchanging; he will continue to have a strong believe in the citizens of the country. The statement is a direct speech, whereby the president is directly referring to the people of Nigeria. The President has high hope and belief in the people to bring Nigeria to greater heights and that he is going to keep being confident in the people.

Excerpt A 4

And my faith in God Almighty, absolute.

Explicit: Explicitly states his faith in God is complete and without doubt.

Implicit: Expresses his humility before God, and suggesting that his leadership is supported by divine will.

The assertion expresses President Bola Ahmed Tinubu's firm belief and strong affirmation in God Almighty. The statement is a direct speech it directly communicates the president's absolute faith in God Almighty. The president has a great belief and trust in God Almighty without questioning; he believes that God Almighty will be in all his affairs.

Excerpt A5

I know that His hand shall provide the needed moral strength and clarity of purpose in those instances when we seem to have reached the limits of our human capacity.

Explicit: Explicitly states his belief that God will step in to provide moral strength and clear direction in the path he has taken.

Implicit: Expresses his reduction of the weight of responsibility on himself, by showing that God is the ultimate guide.

This is a continuation of the faith the president has on God. It expresses President Bola Ahmed Tinubu's firm belief in the God Almighty. The President believes he will be in all affairs and situations in his life and that he shall intervene to guide, and protect, whatever comes his way, the President believes that God will provide moral strength and clarity of purpose in difficult situations. The direct speech act is used in this sentence. President Bola Ahmed Tinubu directly communicates his belief in the Almighty God.

4.1.2 ASSERTIVE SPEECH ACTS IN THE INAUGURAL SPEECH OF PRESIDENT MUHAMMADU BUHARI

Excerpt B 3

Nigerians have shown their commitment to democracy and are determined to entrench its culture.

Explicit: Affirms that Nigerians are dedicated to strengthening democracy

Implicit: Expresses a strategic legitimization and unifying act, it praises the electorate to validate his leadership, reinforces democracy as a national identity, and motivates citizens to continue sustaining democratic culture. Projecting Nigeria as a resilient democracy to the outside world. This is an assertion stated by President Muhammadu Buhari because it carries the value of truth of how Nigerians have shown commitment to democracy 1960 to -date. The speech act used is directly referring to the citizens of Nigeria. The direction of fit used is words to world, where President tries to make the words fit to state of affairs.

Excerpt B7

Together we co-operated to surprise the world that had come to expect only the worst from Nigeria.

Explicit: Notes that Nigerian's cooperation has shocked the world that doubted them.

Implicit: Expresses national branding and unity act to reconstructs Nigeria's global image from failure to resilience, encourages citizens to see themselves capable of greatness when united, and legitimizes democracy by showing that peaceful cooperation produces stability and progress.

This statement is an assertive of fact, the President is talking about how Nigerians have cooperated and surprised the countries or people that expected the worst. The people that expect nothing from Nigeria but failure, that Nigeria can never be great again. The President claims that Nigerians have come together to surprise the world that she shall be great again in all aspects.

Table 1. PRESIDENT BOLA AHMED TINUBU’S INAUGURAL SPEECH (SPEECH A)

SPEECH ACTS (DIRECT AND INDIRECT)	Frequency	Percentage
Assertive	35	87.5
Expressive	0	0
Commissive	2	5
Directive	1	2.5
Declarative	2	5
TOTAL	40	100

Table 2 PRESIDENT MUHAMMADU BUHARI’S INAUGURAL SPEECH (SPEECH B)

SPEECH ACTS (DIRECT AND INDIRECT)	Frequency	Percentage
Assertive	17	42.5
Expressive	8	20
Commissive	12	30
Directive	2	5
Declarative	1	2.5
TOTAL	40	100%

Table 1, shows that assertive constitute 85% of the speech acts from the inaugural speech of President Bola Ahmed Tinubu. While, table 2, President Muhammadu Buharis use of assertive speech equals 42%. This shows that generally, assertive is the most used speech act in their Inaugural Speeches. Particularly, in President Bola

Ahmed Tinubu’s Inaugural speech assertive is dominant constituting three-quarter of the total illocutionary acts contained in his address. The predominance of assertive is in relation with the findings of Ayeomoni & Akinkuolere (2012) which identified the majority of assertive illocutionary acts in other similar speeches. However, President Buhari’s military background and anti-corruption stance has shaped his use of assertive in his speech. Therefore, the speech focuses on stability, discipline and restoration, thereby portrays strong belief in Nigeria is potential despite its problems, which aligns with his leadership style that focuses on resilience and national unity. With regards to President Tunibu, his experience as a pragmatic leader and former governor of Lagos state, his statements, such as ‘‘ the work of rebuilding Nigeria starts now and ‘‘we will restore prosperity and equity to every Nigerian’’ highlight his focus on economic growth, reforms and national unity. His speech uses Assertive to project action-oriented leadership and inclusion of his vision, President Tinubu intends to convey a message of a renewed hope and practical solutions for Nigeria’s challenges. Therefore, both use assertive speech act to commit to the truth condition of the world that is to say they use the assertive speech acts to show that they know what is happening in the world and that they will do everything within their powers to avert it. They use speech acts to show to the citizens of Nigeria that they know the challenges country facing.

In an excerpt, President Bola Ahmed Tinubu said: This nation’s journey has been shaped by the prayers of millions, and the collective sacrifices of us all. What can be deduce here is, President Tunibu is in the picture of the many prayers by Nigerians for the country to be great again and the sacrifices made by the Nigeria citizens fort progress in all state of affairs. The personal inclination of President Bola Ahmed

Tinubu and President Muhammadu Buhari is to constantly reassure Nigerians of their willingness to tackle the numerous socio-economic, agricultural, insecurity challenges in Nigeria.

One of the reason for the presidents being assertive in their inaugurals speeches is to show commitments. And less of persuasions in their inaugurals than in campaign speeches where by it is more of persuasion and the use of commissive speech acts (Trosborg 2000 cited in Boakye 2014) campaign speeches are more likely to use commissives to gain more votes, inaugurals, which are occasional speeches do not require a lot of persuasion than assertive.

FINDING

The study, found out that assertive speech act is the most dominant act in both speeches that is to say president Bola Ahmed make use of assertive more in his speech than other speech acts, they both use of assertive by committing to the truth condition of the expressed sentences. In other words, the study contributes to knowledge by finding out that both president Bola Ahmed Tinubu and President Muhammadu Buhari use Assertive speech acts more in their campaign speech by committing to the truth condition. Some of the reasons the presidents being more assertive in their inaugurals because of less instances in the use of persuasive in their inaugurals than in campaign speeches. (Trosborg 2000 cited in Boakye 2014) campaign speeches are more likely to use commissures to gain more votes since, inaugurals are occasional speeches and do not require a lot of persuasion other than assertive. The findings disagree with the findings of Olaniyi (2010) which concludes that inaugural speeches are used to make promises to the audience. It agrees with the findings of Ayeomoni & Akinkuolere (2012) that assertive illocutionary acts is the most dominant speech act in the presidential inaugural speeches. Another reason both

Presidents use assertive is to commit to the truth condition of state of affairs in the country so as to show Nigerians that they know the struggles and challenges been faced by the citizens of Nigeria so as to give them hope that Nigeria will be great again. They use assertive to state the challenges like insecurity, Job opportunity and many others that are been faced by the citizens.

CONCLUSION

The paper examine the speech act used in the inaugural speeches of President Bola Ahmed Tinubu and President Muhammadu Buhari by extracting Data from the downloaded version of the inaugural speech via www.dailytrust.com, speech acts as proposed by Searle(1969), has been examined in both speeches, also the dominant speech act has also been examined in both speeches. The use the assertive speech act both Presidents to commit to the actuality of what they express using the verbs stating, affirming, believing, which help them to express that they know the challenges and struggles been faced by Nigerians such as insecurity, job opportunities which help them communicate the communicative aim of the inaugural speeches

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